

A STUDY ON THE SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF THE AGRICULTURE SECTOR IN KARNATAKA

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Abstract

The present study explores the concept of sustainable agriculture, which refers to farming practices that meet society's current food and textile needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Sustainable agriculture emphasizes the responsible use of natural resources and ecosystem services, integrating environmental health, economic profitability, and social equity into agricultural development. There are various methods to enhance the sustainability of the agricultural sector, including improved resource management, eco-friendly technologies, and conservation practices. Agriculture has historically been one of the primary and traditional occupations in Karnataka. It remains a major source of livelihood for a large segment of the population and continues to be the backbone of the state's economy. For Karnataka, with its diverse agro-climatic zones and a mix of rain-fed and irrigated areas, achieving sustainability in agriculture is critical for long-term food security and rural development. This study aims to analyze the trends in agricultural growth, productivity, resource use, and policy interventions in Karnataka over recent years. By identifying key patterns and evaluating sustainability indicators, the research intends to provide insights into how the state's agriculture sector can transition toward a more resilient and sustainable future. This study analyses the area, production, and productivity of the agriculture sector in Karnataka and identifies the social factors of the sustainable agriculture sector. The growth in the area and production of different major crops in Karnataka were estimated using the compound growth function and correlation. The necessary secondary data were collected for 6

years from 2015-16 to 2020-21. The research used statistical tools like percentages, compound annual growth rate (CAGR), and correlation, which were analysed through Excel and SPSS 21 statistical software. Growth rates showed a significant positive growth in the area of total cereals, pulses, food grains, oilseeds, and commercial crops showed positive growth.

Keywords: Growth, Development, Major Crops, Area, and Production.

Introduction

A sustainable agriculture approach seeks to utilize natural resources in such a way that they can regenerate their productive capacity, and also minimize harmful impacts on ecosystems beyond a field's edge. It can be based on an understanding of ecosystem services. Agriculture sector has a vast environmental footprint, playing a major role in causing climate change, water scarcity, water pollution, land degradation, deforestation and other processes; it is simultaneously causing environmental changes and being impacted by these changes. Sustainable agriculture consists of environment friendly methods of farming that allow the production of crops or livestock without damage to human or natural systems. It involves preventing adverse effects to soil, water, biodiversity, surrounding or downstream resources as well as to those working or living on the farm or in neighboring areas. Elements of sustainable agriculture can include permaculture, agroforestry, mixed farming, multiple cropping, and crop rotation. The elasticity of India's agriculture sector can be seen from the fact that despite the COVID-19 pandemic, its performance in output was strong. As per Census 2011, about 30% of the total workers in the state are still engaged in agricultural and allied sector activities, which accounts for about 8.73% of the Karnataka's Gross State Value Added (GSVA) for the year 2019-20 (at constant prices). The main crops grown are Rice, Ragi, Jowar (sorghum), maize, and pulses (Tur and gram) in addition to oilseeds and a number of other cash crops. Cashews, coconut, arecanut, cardamom,

chillies, cotton, sugarcane and tobacco are also produced. Karnataka is the largest producer of coarse cereals, coffee, raw silk and tomatoes among the states in India. Horticultural crops are grown in an area of 16,300 km² and the annual production is about 9.58 million tons. The income generated from horticulture constitutes over 40% of income generated from agriculture and it is about 17 per cent of the state's GDP.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the performance of sustainable development in the agriculture sector of Karnataka state.
2. To analyze the trends in the growth of area and production of the agriculture sector in the state.

Hypothesis of the Study

1. There is a significant relationship between area and production of the sustainable agriculture sector in Karnataka.

Research Methodology

The study is mainly based on secondary data information. It has been collected from various annual reports of Central Statistics Office, Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation, Government of India, Minister of Agriculture and Farmers Welfare, Economic Survey of India and Karnataka (2020-21), Directorate of Economics and Statistics, journals, articles etc. The research paper was study period from 2015-16 to 2019-20. The study was statistical tools used like Percentages and Compound Annual Growth Rate (CAGR) and Correlation were analyzed through excel and SPSS 21 statistical software.

Agriculture Sector in Karnataka

Agriculture sector is the main source of income and employment for the rural people of Karnataka as majority of the rural population is dependent on agriculture and its allied sectors. Karnataka is divided in ten agro-climatic zones, taking into consideration the rainfall pattern, soil types, texture, depth and physio-chemical properties, elevation, topography, major crops and the type of vegetation. The contribution of Agriculture sector to the overall GSDP saw an increase from 12.16 per cent to 13.15 per cent in 2020-21 against 2019-20. As per the 2011 Census, about 30 per cent of the total workers in the state are still engaged in agricultural and allied sector activities, which accounts for about 8.73 per cent of the Karnataka's GSVA for the year 2019-20 (at constant prices). In Karnataka, agriculture has occupied about 12.31 million hectares of land, which includes 64.6 per cent of the total area. The main season for sustainable agriculture in the state is monsoon as irrigation is done in 26.5 per cent of the total cropped area. The principal cropping pattern of the region is influenced not only by agro-climatic conditions like rainfall, soil, and temperature, etc. but also by State Government policies and schemes for crop production in the form of subsidies, tariff and speed of infrastructure development

Growth in Trends of Major Crops: Area and Production

The 2nd Advance Estimates of Production (2020-21) based on area coverage under major crops during kharif, rabi and summer seasons, loss of crops due to excess rains/ floods in some parts indicate likely production of 117.38 lakh tonnes cereals and 19.28 lakh tonnes of pulses against the target of 110.02 and 23.03 lakh tonnes, respectively. Oilseeds production is estimated to be 11.46 lakh tonnes against the target of 13.05 lakh tonnes. Production of cotton is likely to be 19.11 lakh bales against the target of 13.90 lakh bales.

Table - 1
Season-wise Area of Principal Crops in Karnataka from 2017-18 to 2020-21

(Unit: Area in Lakh Hectares)

Crop / Group	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Kharif				
Cereals	30.00	30.46	35.04	35.65
Pulses	16.02	16.34	22.49	22.06
Total food grains	46.02	46.80	57.53	57.71
Oilseeds	8.27	8.91	8.93	9.46
Cotton	5.21	4.71	8.03	7.50
Sugarcane	4.00	4.00	4.29	4.50
Tobacco	0.95	0.93	0.95	0.70
Annual	110.47	112.15	137.26	137.58
Rabi				
Cereals	13.60	10.45	10.55	8.84
Pulses	14.16	12.40	10.23	9.92
Total food grains	27.76	22.85	20.78	18.76
Oilseeds	0.97	1.48	0.55	0.78
Cotton	0.26	0.07	0.14	0.15
Sugarcane	-	-	-	-
Tobacco	-	-	-	-
Annual	56.75	47.25	42.25	38.45
Summer				
Cereals	2.64	1.72	3.26	2.60
Pulses	0.057	0.18	0.05	0.08
Total food grains	2.697	1.90	3.31	2.68
Oilseeds	1.75	2.05	1.18	1.85

Cotton	-	-	-	-
Sugarcane	-	-	-	-
Tobacco	-	-	-	-
Annual	7.144	5.85	7.8	7.21

Source: Government of Karnataka (2020), Department of Agriculture, Planning Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Bengaluru – 2020-21.

Table-1 gives the information about the season-wise area of principal crops in Karnataka from 2017-18 to 2020-21. Under the Kharif season, the area of major crops in the agriculture sector is 11047 lakh ha in 2017-18, which has increased to 137.58 lakh ha in 2020-21. During the Rabi season, during 2017-18, the area of major crops in the agriculture sector is 56.75 lakh ha, which has decreased to 38.45 lakh ha in 2020-21. During the summer season, the area of major crops in the agriculture sector increased trends from 7.144 lakh ha in 2017-18 to 7.21 lakh ha in 2020-21.

Table - 2
Season-wise Production of Principal Crops in Karnataka from 2017-18 to 2020-21
(Unit: Lakh Tonnes, Cotton in Lakh bales of 170 Kgs in lint form)

Crop / Group	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	2020-21
Kharif				
Cereals	93.00	70.77	90.38	99.38
Pulses	11.42	8.32	14.07	13.18
Total food grains	104.42	79.09	104.45	112.56
Oilseeds	10.02	7.39	8.59	9.18
Cotton	18.25	9.21	23.19	19.11
Sugarcane	315.00	322.15	360.34	410.40
Tobacco	0.89	0.73	0.83	0.54
Annual	553.00	497.66	601.85	664.27
Rabi				
Cereals	18.48	10.78	14.67	9.93

Pulses	10.67	5.88	7.47	6.08
Total food grains	29.15	16.66	22.14	16.01
Oilseeds	0.73	1.25	0.49	0.52
Cotton	0.19	0.06	0.10	0.08
Sugarcane	-	-	-	-
Tobacco	-	-	-	-
Annual	59.22	34.63	44.87	32.62
Summer				
Cereals	8.12	5.06	9.81	8.07
Pulses	0.017	0.006	0.011	0.02
Total food grains	8.137	5.12	9.82	8.09
Oilseeds	2.04	2.03	1.32	1.76
Cotton	0.06	-	-	-
Sugarcane	-	-	-	-
Tobacco	-	-	-	-
Annual	18.374	12.216	20.961	17.94

Source: Government of Karnataka (2020), Department of Agriculture, Planning Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Bengaluru – 2020-21.

The above Table–2 indicates the season-wise production of principal crops in Karnataka from 2017-18 to 2020-21. During the Kharif season, the annual crop predominately increasing production of principal crops in the agriculture sector is 553.00 in 2017-18, which has grown to 664.27 in 2020-21. In the Rabi season, the annual production of major crops is 59.22 in 2017-18, which sharply decreased to 32.62 in 2020-21. During the summer season of 2017-18, the annual major crops of the agriculture sector are 18.374, this decreased to 17.94 in 2020-21.

Table - 3

Area of Principal Crops in Karnataka from 2017-18 to 2020-21

(Unit: Area in Lakh Hectares)

Crop	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	CAGR (%)
Rice	11.10	10.34	9.93	11.99	12.48	3.90
Jowar	11.04	9.48	10.88	9.94	9.14	-3.25
Ragi	7.05	5.98	7.78	5.55	6.74	-1.63
Maize	12.20	13.70	13.07	14.09	15.00	4.51
Bajra	1.66	2.42	2.32	1.94	3.39	12.83
Wheat	1.74	1.68	1.93	1.58	1.58	-2.51
Minor millets	0.28	0.21	0.37	0.19	0.52	12.05
Total cereals	45.07	43.81	46.27	45.28	48.85	1.96
Tur	6.57	12.14	8.85	15.61	16.26	22.92
Total pulses	28.31	29.66	30.26	35.70	32.77	4.90
Total food grains	73.38	73.47	76.53	80.98	81.62	3.15
Groundnut	5.70	6.66	5.65	5.41	5.30	-3.47
Total oilseeds	12.86	12.93	11.00	9.99	10.66	-6.14
Cotton	6.42	5.10	5.47	7.18	8.17	8.59
Sugarcane	6.02	4.88	5.33	7.94	7.65	10.14
Tobacco	0.84	0.90	0.95	0.88	0.95	2.26
Areca nut (Processed)	2.48	2.55	2.79	4.76	5.00	22.46
Coconut	4.41	4.37	4.46	6.10	6.10	10.32
Dry chillies	1.02	1.28	1.02	1.58	0.74	-4.22
Pepper	0.35	0.38	0.41	1.48	1.61	55.45
Cardamom	0.18	0.17	0.15	0.02	0.02	-47.98

Source: Government of Karnataka (2020), Department of Agriculture, Planning Programme Monitoring and Statistics Department, Bengaluru – 2020-21.

The area of principal crops in the agriculture sector during the period from 2015-16 to 2019-20, in terms of lakh ha, is presented in Table-3 and Graph-3. It is clear that the major crops like total cereals, pulses, food grains, oilseeds, cotton, sugarcane, and tobacco. During 2015-16, the total cereals area was 45.07 lakh ha, which

predominantly increased to 48.85 lakh ha in 2019-20. The total pulses area is 28.31 lakh ha in 2015-16, which has increased to 32.77 lakh ha in 2019-20. In 2015-16, the total food grains area was 73.38 lakh ha, which increased to 81.62 lakh ha in 2019-20. The total oilseed of area position is 12.86 lakh ha in 2015-16, which increased to 12.93 lakh ha in 2016-17, and then it has decreased to 10.66 lakh ha in 2019-20.

The above table shows the CAGR for area of major crops in the agriculture sector in the state during the period between 2015-16 and 2019-20. The CAGR for the major crops of total cereals is 1.96 per cent, followed by the total pulses (4.90%), total food grains (3.15%), total oilseeds (-6.14%), cotton (8.59%), sugarcane (10.14%), tobacco (2.26%) and other commercial crops showed in above Table-3.

Table – 4
Production of Principal Crops in Karnataka from 2017-18 to 2019-20

(Unit: Lakh Tonnes, Cotton in Lakh bales of 170 Kg in Lint form)

Crop	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	CAGR (%)
Rice	30.21	28.74	29.40	34.58	39.48	7.47
Jowar	7.96	8.46	12.01	9.31	10.45	6.61
Ragi	11.88	4.91	15.41	6.78	11.62	2.82
Maize	33.10	33.14	55.52	37.77	47.46	8.89
Bajra	1.11	2.55	3.53	1.77	3.67	22.46
Wheat	1.56	1.71	2.24	1.63	1.80	2.41
Minor millets	0.10	0.07	0.25	0.16	0.38	41.86
Total cereals	85.92	79.85	118.38	92.00	114.86	7.49
Tur	2.42	12.12	8.13	9.47	11.26	32.69
Total pulses	10.52	20.41	21.53	18.46	21.55	14.27
Total food grains	96.44	99.99	139.91	110.46	136.41	8.25
Groundnut	3.95	4.19	5.99	3.97	5.03	4.39
Total oilseeds	7.09	8.05	12.20	7.92	10.41	7.81
Cotton	11.52	10.24	17.71	14.00	23.29	18.78
Sugarcane *	363.14	273.38	374.61	424.11	360.34	4.33
Tobacco	0.49	0.65	0.95	0.71	0.83	12.10
Areca nut (processed)	4.86	5.17	5.10	8.51	10.82	23.36

Coconut (Million Nuts)	3688.82	3417.20	3284.69	4321.76	5030.77	8.93
Dry chillies	1.03	2.60	2.07	1.96	1.29	1.69
Pepper (Lakh Quintals)	2.68	2.29	2.57	9.41	6.30	36.65
Cardamom	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.002	0.003	-37.57

Source: Government of Karnataka (2020), Final Estimates of Directorate of Economics & Statistics – 2015 to 2019.

Note: *Sugarcane production for harvested area of 4.00 lakh ha.in 2017-18, 4.96 lakh ha, in 2018-19 & 4.29 lakh ha, in 2019-20.

Table show the production of principal crops in the agriculture sector during the period from 2015-16 to 2019-20, in terms of lakh tonnes. It is clear from the above table, the production of principal crops in the agriculture sector like total cereals, pulses, food grains, oilseeds, cotton, sugarcane, and tobacco. During 2015-16, the production of total cereals was 85.92 lakh tonnes, which significantly increased to 114.86 lakh tonnes in 2019-20. The total pulses production was 10.52lakh tonnes in 2015-16, which has increased to 21.53lakh tonnes in 2017-18; then it has decreased to 18.46 lakh tonnes in 2018-19; and then it has sharply increased to 21.55 lakh tonnes in 2019-20. In 2015-16, the production of total food grains was 96.44 lakh tonnes, which increased to 136.41 lakh tonnes in 2019-20. The total oilseed of production position was 7.09 lakh tonnes in 2015-16, which increased to 12.20 lakh tonnes in 2017-18; then it has decreased to 7.92 lakh tonnes in 2018-19; and then it has sharply increased to 10.41 lakh tonnes in 2019-20. The commercial major crops like cotton, sugarcane, tobacco, etc.

The total production of cotton was 11.52 lakh bales in 2015-16, which significantly increased to 23.29 lakh bales in 2019-20. The production of sugarcane was 363.14 lakh tonnes in 2015-16, which increased to 424.11 lakh tonnes in 2018-19; and then it has sharply decreased to 360.34 lakh tonnes in 2019-20. The tobacco production was 0.49 lakh tonnes in 2015-16; which increased to 0.83 lakh tonnes in 2019-20. The above table also illustrations the CAGR for production of principal crops in the agriculture sector during the period between 2015-16 and 2019-20. The CAGR for the

production of principal crops of total cereals is 7.49 per cent, followed by the total pulses (14.27%), total food grains (8.25%), total oilseeds (7.81%), cotton (18.78%), sugarcane (4.33%), tobacco (12.40%) and other commercial crops showed in above Table-4.

Testing Hypothesis

H0: There is no significant relationship between area and production of the sustainable agriculture sector in Karnataka.

H1: There is a significant relationship between area and production of the sustainable agriculture sector in Karnataka.

Table - 5

Correlation Results of Area and Production of Agriculture Sector in Karnataka

Variables	Mean	Std. Devi	Pearson Correlation	Sig.
Agriculture Area	204.8400	10.45699	.647*	0.238
Agriculture Production	617.6660	82.21006		

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

From the above Table–5 details of the correlation between area and production of agriculture sector in Karnataka. The calculated mean values of agriculture area and agriculture production are 204.8400 and 10.45699 respectively. The tested standard deviation values of agriculture area and agriculture production are 617.6660 and 82.21006 respectively. The tested Pearson correlation value is .647, at significant 10% level. However, the null hypothesis accepted and the alternative rejected. Hence, it implies that there is a significant relationship between agriculture area and production of agriculture sector in Karnataka.

Conclusion

Karnataka state is considered a tiny part of India, as it reveals significant features of the country in climate, soil types, rainfall, crops grown, and a variety of natural resources. It has ideal soil and climate suited for raising a different variety of principal crops; tropical region, temperate region, humid and arid regions are grown in the state. Karnataka economy is one of the furthermost important attributes of the agriculture sector. Sustainable agriculture is considered to be one of the primary occupations for the inhabitants in the state. In Karnataka, the majority of the people are involved in growing crops especially in the rural areas. Sustainable agriculture is considered to be one of the major occupations for the inhabitants of the state. The majority of the people in the state are engaged in growing crops, particularly in rural areas. The present research papers analyze the growth in trends of area and production of the agriculture sector and it has find out the relationship between area and production of agriculture in the state. This study found from the correlation between area and production of agriculture sector in Karnataka. The calculated mean values of agriculture area and agriculture production are 204.8400 and 10.45699 respectively. The tested standard deviation values of agriculture area and agriculture production are 617.6660 and 82.21006 respectively. The tested Pearson correlation value is .647, at significant 10% level.

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